

GENERAL ASPECTS OF MEDICAL CARE ASSESSMENT

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Abstract. *The strategic goal of reforming the healthcare system in our country is to practically ensure the right of citizens to qualified medical care, while the protection of children's health is a priority task of the state, and the improvement of medical care requires a complex of various measures. At the same time, it should be noted that identifying and eliminating shortcomings in the provision of medical care is the simplest, most convenient, and effective way to improve the quality of this activity.*

Keywords: *defects of medical care, forensic medical examination*

Since the protection of children's health is a priority task of the state, the main goal of the healthcare system is to improve the accessibility and quality of medical care for the preservation and strengthening of the health of the younger generation, which is reflected in current regulatory legal acts. In this regard, reducing infant mortality is one of the important tasks of the state, and according to WHO recommendations, this indicator is one of the leading indicators not only of the health and standard of living of the population, but also of the quality of the healthcare system. According to WHO criteria, quality medical care must comply with the standards of current medical technologies and satisfy the patient's needs. Consequently, the formation of a standardization system in healthcare is extremely important in regulating treatment and diagnostic processes, and in controlling the activities of medical institutions. Diagnostic and treatment standards have been developed in all areas of healthcare, including the provision of medical care to children. They indicate the volume of medical procedures that must be performed, which does not preclude additional examinations or procedures beyond this volume. Due to their sensitivity to various influences and changes in environmental conditions, the issues of studying the health status of children under one year of age, improving their physical development, and reducing morbidity and mortality are relevant. Consequently, during this period, along with high rates of physical development, morbidity and mortality rates are relatively high. The concept of quality of medical care is currently included in the system of final results of the activities of healthcare institutions and is determined by a number of objective and subjective criteria. This refers to the proportionality, effectiveness, and compliance of medical care with scientific and technological achievements. Currently, the issue of assessing the quality of medical care provided to children worldwide is at

the center of attention of researchers and healthcare organizers. At the same time, researchers note the absence of universal indicators for assessing the quality of medical care. Although WHO standards are understandable in the current format, they do not always facilitate an adequate assessment of the quality of medical care measures.

It was noted that currently, the satisfaction of citizens with medical services, that is, the full coverage of their needs in this area, is considered one of the main criteria for determining the quality and convenience of medical care. This situation is assessed using objective and subjective methods. Researchers recommend conducting social surveys of parents or close relatives of children and doctors using questionnaires for subjective assessment of this issue. Analyzing the legal and socio-psychological aspects of determining the quality of pediatric care, he emphasizes the need to improve the relationship between doctors and parents of patients, increasing the legal literacy of both parties to prevent conflict situations. In addition, it is necessary to train medical workers in conflict-free interaction with patients, improve the mechanisms for effective consideration of citizens' complaints in medical institutions, and create an atmosphere of psychological comfort between patients, their parents, and medical workers. In some European countries, strategic programs have been developed aimed at improving the quality of medical care for the population. An example is the Iberian program for training personnel and implementing measures to provide high-quality primary health care in Spain. Due to the relevance of the issue of children's health, it is at the center of constant attention of representatives of various fields of medicine. The topic of preserving children's health and improving the quality of life, improving the organization and provision of medical care for them has been widely covered, especially by specialists in the field of healthcare organization. In particular, in Russia alone, over the past two decades, specialists in this field have conducted a number of large-scale dissertation studies on improving the provision of medical care to children in general and in cases of individual diseases, including for obtaining a doctoral degree. A person is born, grows, lives, and works in a specific environment and environment, and these undoubtedly affect their health. These factors, according to the WHO, are called social determinants of health. The formation of these conditions depends, first of all, on state policy in the field of healthcare, the financing and distribution of various - biological, environmental, and social resources. These issues constitute the subject of social pediatrics.

Analyzing the effectiveness of medical and social assistance provided to children, he notes a number of organizational problems, such as insufficient legal knowledge among specialists, a low level of consistency between medical institutions, and imperfections in the interaction of various departments and specialists in various fields. Undoubtedly, the mother's health, especially the course of pregnancy, will

subsequently affect the health of the children. At the same time, it is important to take into account the risk factors that are significant in the development of pregnancy pathology and to eliminate them as much as possible.

The rate of errors is higher in children requiring specific medical care and in cases where complex medical technologies are used. At the same time, the reporting rate of medical errors is generally higher in public institutions than in private hospitals. This situation is an administrative problem in the verification of errors in medical care.

Other authors also believe that, while respecting the autonomy of patients, openly explaining to them the mistakes and apologizing will prevent the emergence of various complaints, objections, and claims regarding this situation in the future.

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